

**Location Matters:
Everyday Gender Discrimination in Remote and On-site Work**
Forthcoming at *Organization Science*

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September 2024

ABSTRACT

Remote work has dramatically transformed professional environments, sparking considerable scholarly interest in its impact on employees and organizations. Contributing to this burgeoning literature, we investigate how remote versus on-site work affects women’s experiences of gender discrimination. Given that work location can alter the gendered nature of interactions, we focus on everyday gender discrimination—slights and offenses that occur in interactions and are perceived by recipients as reflecting gender bias. Integrating gender frame theory and scholarship on virtual work, we argue that the gender frame tends to be less salient in remote settings. Thus, we predict that women will experience less everyday gender discrimination when working remotely than on-site. Moreover, because the gender frame is likely to be more salient during on-site work for younger women and those who work with mostly men, we expect that these women will experience a particularly pronounced reduction in everyday gender discrimination when working remotely. To test these predictions, we developed a new measure of everyday gender discrimination and conducted an original survey of 1,091 professional women who work in the same job both remotely and on-site. We find that women consistently report less everyday gender discrimination in remote versus on-site work. This effect is particularly pronounced for younger women and those who interact mainly with men. Overall, this study advances research on how work location shapes workers’ outcomes and experiences, enriches the literature on the trade-offs women face in virtual and on-site settings, and extends scholarship on the contextual factors shaping workplace discrimination.

Keywords: Future of work, gender, discrimination, work from home, remote work, hybrid work

For their comments on previous drafts, we are grateful to Santiago Campero, Clayton Childress, Alexis Dennis, Alicia Eads, Solène Delecourt, Stefan Dimitriadis, Angelina Grigoryeva, Joyce He, Sonia Kang, Ryann Manning, Jenna Myers, Jayanti Owens, Tiantian Yang, and the Toronto Group of Seven. We thank Jennifer Merluzzi for her editorial guidance and two anonymous reviewers for their constructive suggestions. We also appreciate feedback from audience members at the Wharton People and Organizations Annual Conference, the Frankfurt School of Finance and Management, and the American Sociological Association Annual Meeting. We thank Abigail Mengist, Jessica Wei, Vincent Zhang, and Zixin Zhang for their excellent research assistance. Additionally, we gratefully acknowledge funding support from the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada, the Canada Research Chairs Program, and the Institute for Pandemics and the Institute for Gender and the Economy at the University of Toronto.

INTRODUCTION

New communication technologies have transformed contemporary work, allowing individuals to work in remote locations alongside traditional, on-site settings. As professional work becomes increasingly untethered from central, physical workplaces, researchers have examined how work location influences workers' productivity (Barrero et al. 2023), social networks (Rockmann and Pratt 2015), management styles (Conzon 2023), and developmental opportunities (Emanuel et al. 2023). This literature demonstrates how workers' interactions, experiences, and career prospects can differ between remote and on-site settings. Although studies in this vein have begun to examine how work location generates social inequalities (e.g., Conzon 2023, Emanuel et al. 2023), limited research has examined how work location might influence discriminatory interactions, particularly those shaped by gender bias.

Contributing to the burgeoning organizational literature on remote work, we ask: How does working remotely versus on-site influence women's likelihood of experiencing gender discrimination? Although gender discrimination takes many forms (e.g., Coffman et al. 2021, Leung and Koppman 2018, Merluzzi and Phillips 2022), we focus on discrimination experiences that occur via interpersonal interactions. Such *everyday gender discrimination* consists of the slights and offenses that occur in interactions and that recipients perceive to be motivated by gender bias (Ridgeway and Correll 2004). Interactions are a central vehicle by which gendered beliefs are expressed and reinforced (Ridgeway 1997), as well as a key mechanism for enacting and maintaining gender stereotypes (West and Zimmerman 1987). Because work location can alter the gendered nature of interactions (e.g., Fisk and Ridgeway 2018), it has the potential to change women's experience of everyday gender discrimination.

Everyday discrimination includes, for example, colleagues or clients ignoring a woman's contributions, making inappropriate comments, or asking her to perform tasks unrelated to her job because of her gender. Any single instance of everyday gender discrimination may appear inconsequential, but the cumulative effects can be significant. When people regularly experience slights or offenses at work, they may feel frustrated, develop strained relationships with co-workers

(Karunakaran 2022), become less likely to perceive their workplaces as fair, and become less satisfied with their jobs (Rosigno et al. 2021). Simply perceiving that one has been the victim of discrimination can have profound health and performance consequences for workers (Ensher et al. 2001, Masterson et al. 2000, Williams et al. 2008) as well as negative ramifications for organizations, including employee turnover or legal action (Goldman et al. 2006, Madera et al. 2012). Given the importance of everyday gender discrimination for employees and organizations, it is imperative to understand how work location might influence such gendered interactions.

We draw on gender frame theory (Ridgeway 1997, 2011, Ridgeway and Correll 2004) to ground our expectations about work location and everyday gender discrimination. Gender frame theory emphasizes that gender serves as a primary cultural frame for coordinating social behavior. At work, the extent to which people use gender as a frame for organizing expectations and behavior varies with the environment. Both gender scholars and those who study virtual communication have suggested that virtual settings like remote work might transmit fewer social cues that signal gender (Bommer and Schmidtke 2022, Canedo et al. 2022, Fisk and Ridgeway 2018), thus reducing gender frame salience. Bringing together these two streams of research, we expect that the gender frame will be less salient in remote work and, consequently, women will experience less everyday gender discrimination. We further draw on gender frame theory to anticipate the individual and contextual characteristics that intersect with gender to amplify its salience during in-person, on-site interactions (Daldrop et al. 2023, Qian and Fan 2019, Ridgeway 2011). We argue that the gender frame is likely to be particularly salient during on-site work for women who are younger and women who work with only or mostly men. As a result of high on-site gender salience, we expect that these women will experience a more pronounced reduction in gender discrimination when working remotely versus on-site.

We test these expectations using a novel survey with two notable characteristics. First, we surveyed professional women who work in the same job remotely and on-site. This within-subject design allows us to hold constant individual, job, and organizational factors that are constant across work

locations (e.g., socioeconomic status, work role, industry). Second, we designed a new measure of everyday gender discrimination to capture negative gendered experiences in remote and on-site work. Our approach focuses on women's perceptions of discrimination, which can powerfully influence workers' health, task performance, and job satisfaction (Cortina et al. 2001, Lamont et al. 2016, Mong and Roscigno 2010, Roscigno et al. 2021).

Everyday gender discrimination is a particularly appropriate outcome to compare across remote and on-site locations. Such incidents can be pinpointed to particular moments and locations (e.g., a dismissive comment during a digital or in-person meeting), allowing for a comparison of respondents' experiences when working remotely versus on-site. In contrast, other outcomes in discrimination research, such as hiring rates or wage disparities, cannot be unambiguously tied to specific locations.

Consistent with theoretical expectations, results show that professional women experience less everyday gender discrimination in remote versus on-site work. This result is robust across numerous specifications and subsamples, including controlling for the frequency of formal and informal interactions in remote and on-site locations. Descriptive analyses show that women generally experience similar types of discrimination in each location, but are less likely to experience discrimination when working remotely. Additionally, when working remotely, younger women and women who work with only or mostly men experience a particularly pronounced reduction in the likelihood of discrimination. Overall, our results demonstrate that professional women experience significantly less everyday gender discrimination when working remotely versus on-site and that this reduction in discrimination is especially pronounced under certain individual and contextual conditions.

This study makes three main contributions. First, we extend the literature on work location and worker outcomes (e.g., Bloom et al. 2022, Bucher and Langley 2016, Gonsalves 2020, Kellogg 2009, Lee 2019, Barrero et al. 2023) by elucidating the effect of work location on everyday gender discrimination, an important outcome previously unaddressed in this literature. Our theoretical framework characterizes the conditions under which work location exerts the greatest influence, revealing that not all women

experience this effect equally. Second, our study contributes to the literature on the complex trade-offs women face in contemporary remote and on-site work (Villamor et al. 2023) by demonstrating that everyday gender discrimination deserves serious consideration when evaluating the (dis)advantages of remote versus on-site settings. While recent studies highlight the benefits of on-site work for women, such as receiving valuable feedback and mentorship (Emanuel et al. 2023) and leveraging distinct managerial strengths (Conzon 2023), our research uncovers a concurrent gender discrimination penalty for women working on-site compared to remotely. Third, we advance scholarship on the contextual factors influencing workplace discrimination (e.g., Glick and Fiske 2007, Hirsh and Kornrich 2008, Kalev et al. 2006, Pager and Shepherd 2008, Quillian and Midtbøen 2021). In contrast to the typical focus on organizational, institutional, and legal conditions in this literature (e.g., Castilla 2015, Dobbin et al. 2015, Rivera 2020, Gorman 2005), we identify on-site versus remote work location as a distinct contextual factor with a substantial effect on workplace discrimination. To that end, our measure of everyday gender discrimination offers a new way to capture the quotidian experience of gender bias in both remote and on-site settings. This measure opens new avenues for studying discrimination beyond hiring and wage disparities, allowing researchers to investigate the experience of gender bias in everyday interactions.

WORK LOCATION AND GENDER DISCRIMINATION

New communication technologies and shifting norms around remote work have increasingly decoupled the *act* of working from central, physical *workplaces* (Cappelli 2021). Many professionals now work at least partially remotely (Parker et al. 2022). Studies show how work location affects outcomes like work performance and social networks (Barrero et al. 2023, Rockmann and Pratt 2015), as well as how it influences social inequalities. For example, studies reveal that, when working in different locations, men and women have distinct ways of managing subordinates (Conzon 2023) and receive different levels of mentoring (Emanuel et al. 2023), although little research has directly compared the incidence of gender discrimination in contemporary remote and on-site work.

Gender Frame Theory

We draw on gender frame theory (Ridgeway 1997, 2011, Ridgeway and Correll 2004) to guide our expectations about work location and gender discrimination. According to gender frame theory, gender serves as a primary cultural frame for coordinating social behavior. At work, the extent to which people use gender as a frame for organizing expectations and behavior varies with the work environment. Many “aspects of the workplace can increase the salience for workers of their identities as men and women and, with that, the likelihood that they introduce gender images, interests, and activities into the everyday culture of the workplace” (Ridgeway 2011, p. 113). When the gender frame is highly salient, people organize their behavior and expectations around gendered schemas; when it is less salient, people’s behavior and expectations are less influenced by gender.

Thus, when the gender frame is salient, the likelihood of gender discrimination against women is higher because gender stereotypes are more likely to influence behavior and judgments (Ridgeway 1997, 2011) and because gender stereotypes tend to reflect beliefs that men are worthier of status and more generally competent than women in professional work contexts (Ridgeway 2011). In contrast, when gender is less salient, the effect of gender stereotypes on behavior and evaluations is weaker, reducing the likelihood of gender discrimination (Ridgeway 1997, 2011).

While a substantial body of research shows that the absence of clear performance information about individuals leads to greater reliance on stereotypes (e.g., England 1994, Botelho and Abraham 2017, Correll and Benard 2006, Correll 2017, Sterling and Merluzzi 2019), gender frame theory focuses on a different aspect of the environment: the availability of social cues signaling gender. This perspective highlights that fewer gendered social cues should result in less stereotyping and discrimination. Consistent with this perspective, recent scholarship in communication studies invoking the social identity model of deindividuation effects (or SIDE model) suggests that when gender is less visible and salient, people rely less on gender stereotypes in interactions (Spears et al. 2012, Spears 2017, see also Lea et al. 2007).

Reduced Gender Salience in Modern Virtual Work

Research on modern virtual work offers reason to expect that gender will be less salient in remote settings. Organizational scholars have observed that in contemporary remote work, employees rely on “lean” communication tools, which convey fewer of the social cues that are present in face-to-face interactions (Villamor et al. 2023). To engage with colleagues and clients remotely, workers use video conferencing, phone calls, and text messages. Compared to the in-person communication that constitutes much of on-site work, remote tools carry fewer social cues that signal gender, such as bodily presence, gestures, style of dress, or tone of voice. As communication scholars have noted, “In face-to-face communication, the concurrent exchange of verbal messages along with appearance, kinesics (body movement and facial expression), vocalics (quality and use of the voice), proxemics (increases, decreases, and uses of space), and haptics (touch) provide an abundance of [social] information all at once” (Walther 2008, p. 395). In contrast, when work interactions are virtual, these nonverbal dimensions of communication and individuals’ physical features tend to be less prominent (e.g., Walther 2008, Lim 2023), thus reducing the transmission of social cues. Even in videoconferencing, participants can typically see others only from the shoulders up, restricting views of physical bodies that remind others of characteristics like gender and limiting the prominence of nonverbal dimensions of communication, such as expansive (versus constricted) postures and assertive (versus tentative) hand and arm gestures, which play an important role in enacting gendered status hierarchies in face-to-face interactions (see Ridgeway 2011, Wareham and Overbeck 2020).

This relative “leanness” of communication tools typically used in modern remote work limits the salience of gender. As Villamor and colleagues (2023, p. 124) note, an “advantage of communication leanness for women is the decreased salience of gender-related social cues that beget gender stereotyping.” Similarly, gender scholars have raised the possibility that virtual settings “could reduce the

importance of the gender frame, given that sex category is often not as immediately apparent in online settings and is not as continuously salient” (Fisk and Ridgeway 2018, p. 166).

Consistent with these observations, research on virtual work suggests that virtual settings transmit fewer social cues about interaction partners than in-person communication, thereby reducing the salience of visible status characteristics like gender. Studies of virtual teams indicate that the use of electronic communication technology mitigates the impact of stereotypes and status differences, potentially because the physical characteristics of individuals in lower-status groups are less salient (Canedo et al. 2022). Research on virtual meetings highlights that gender-based status influences team interactions, with higher-status individuals often dominating face-to-face group interactions. However, these status differences may be less influential in virtual teams because the absence of physical, face-to-face presence can reduce the salience of status characteristics like gender (Bommer and Schmidtke 2022). Research on negotiations also supports this conclusion, suggesting that the reduction of social cues in virtual (versus face-to-face) negotiations lessens the influence of gender role stereotypes and equalizes social interactions (Stuhlmacher et al. 2007).

These observations align with a broader body of research on computer-mediated communication, which suggests that interactions in virtual work settings, as opposed to face-to-face settings, tend to transmit fewer social cues and are less influenced by status characteristics. As Flanagin and colleagues (2002, p. 6) note, “By reducing or eliminating static cues (e.g., cues such as appearance, gesticulation, and facial expression), CMC [computer-mediated communication] ostensibly enables individuals to interact more fully and equally.” For example, a meta-analysis of laboratory experiments shows that members of teams using computer-mediated communication tools have more equal influence than members of groups meeting face-to-face (Rains 2005). In an influential early study on this topic, Dubrovsky, Kiesler, and Sethna (1991) found that during face-to-face meetings, high-status individuals dominated discussions, but when the same groups made decisions via email, the disparities in participation due to status were significantly lower. The literature suggests this is partly because computer-mediated communication tools

dampen the status cues typically present in face-to-face interactions (Rains 2005, see also Purvanova et al. 2021).

Of course, social cues do not disappear altogether in virtual communication. Even in the leanest forms of communication, interaction partners can still recall or intuit others' status characteristics based on names or avatars. The critical difference is that virtual communication makes social cues associated with gender *less* salient; interaction partners are less likely to receive gendered social cues and organize their behavior around them.

Accordingly, because virtual work interactions transmit fewer social cues signaling gender, the gender frame is likely to be less salient—and everyday gender discrimination less prevalent—in remote work versus on-site work. Consistent with this expectation, earlier research found that when working in virtual settings, women reported greater satisfaction with team experiences (Lind 1999) and felt more included in group processes (del Carmen Triana et al. 2012) compared to face-to-face interactions. Similarly, women reported experiencing fewer microaggressions when they worked remotely at least some of the time, compared to when they always worked on-site, according to a recent industry survey (Thomas et al. 2022).

Taken together, our arguments suggest that the communication tools associated with remote (versus on-site) work tend to convey fewer social cues that make gender salient in interactions. With colleagues and clients relying less on gender to guide their expectations and behavior toward women, we anticipate that women will experience less everyday gender discrimination when working remotely. We thus expect:

Hypothesis 1: Professional women will experience less everyday gender discrimination when they work remotely versus on-site.

Amplifying On-Site Gender Salience: The Moderating Effects of Individual and Contextual Characteristics

Above, we described why remote communication tools would reduce gender frame salience and, consequently, everyday gender discrimination. We now ask: under what conditions will remote work yield the most pronounced reductions in discrimination? Guided by prior research, we anticipate that women with particularly high gender salience when working on-site will experience the most pronounced differences in location-based discrimination. Put simply, women with high on-site gender salience (and thus a high likelihood of experiencing discrimination) have more room for noticeable improvement when working remotely compared to women whose gender is less salient on-site.

Gender frame theory emphasizes that certain individual and contextual characteristics intersect with gender to amplify its salience. People rely more or less actively on gender for coordinating behavior depending on individual characteristics, such as age or education, as well as contextual characteristics, like the gender composition of group members (Ridgeway 2011, Ridgeway and Correll 2004, Tak et al. 2019). When working on-site, cues about such characteristics can be communicated readily. On-site, individuals send and receive sensory signals through clothing and body shapes (Rasmussen 2005), the firmness of a handshake (Trethewey 1999), as well as facial movements, postures, and subtle variations in voice tone (Boussalis et al. 2021, Hochschild 1983, Leidner 1993). By comparison, such visual and embodied information is not telegraphed as readily in remote work.

Based on this research, we anticipate that characteristics conveyed primarily through nonverbal cues and sensory signals in face-to-face interactions will heighten gender salience on-site, and that women who experience high on-site gender salience will have more room for a noticeable reduction in discrimination when working remotely. Below, we discuss why on-site gender salience would be especially high on-site for young women and those who interact with all or mostly men—and why these women have the potential to experience the most significant reductions in discrimination when working remotely.

Individual Moderator: Age

Age and gender can intersect in ways that amplify gender salience. As Ridgeway (2011, p. 40) notes, “sex and age will virtually always be primary categories in any society” (see also Brewer 1988, Brewer and Lui 1989). In particular, being *young* is likely to heighten gender salience in ways that trigger everyday gender discrimination. Young women are seen as more prototypically female than older women because they tend to have characteristics that align with stereotypical femininity (i.e., attractiveness, vitality) (Daldrop et al. 2023). Indeed, young female faces are more quickly categorized as “woman” than older female faces (Kloth et al. 2015). In turn, “this greater congruence between stereotypes of women and those of young age makes young women more salient and representative of their group compared to older women” (Daldrop et al. 2023, p. 3).

Notably, the gendered characteristics associated with youth and femininity are communicated through physical bodies (Chudacoff 1989) and thus are likely to be particularly salient on-site. Age is not only a biological marker but a social identity achieved through interactions (Johfre and Saperstein 2023). In an effort to intuit others’ age and organize behavior and expectations accordingly, people rely on embodied cues like dress, gestures, and posture. Because these cues are more salient in person, they should activate social categorization by age and gender (Spears et al. 2012) and thus more powerfully pattern behavior (Ridgeway 2011) during on-site versus remote work.

As youth activates certain gender stereotypes, it is likely to encourage everyday gender discrimination. Young women in the workplace—often defined as 30 years or under (Duncan and Loretto 2004, Gander 2014, Harnois 2015, Mengel et al. 2019)—report that colleagues treat them as less credible and competent than (a) older women and (b) men. As compared to older women in professional workplaces, young women are more likely to report that colleagues treat them as less intelligent and capable (Collins et al. 2017, Duncan and Loretto 2004). Young women in white-collar professions also note that they are taken less seriously. As one young, female manager described in a study of professional women, “You are not necessarily taken seriously, because you are a young woman. Sometimes it is just because you are young, sometimes it is because you are not a man, and sometimes it is both” (Jyrkinen

and McKie 2012, p. 68). In university settings, as well, students appear to discount young female instructors' credibility and competence. In a quasi-experimental context where students were randomly assigned to professors, young female faculty received significantly lower evaluations than young male instructors; however, there was no gender bias against older female instructors (Mengel et al. 2019).¹

Youth can also activate gender stereotypes that emphasize women's sexuality, potentially prompting discriminatory expectations and behaviors. This tendency is particularly pronounced on-site, where bodies are physically co-present. As researchers argue, physical bodies are a central vehicle through which age becomes socially constructed and used as a tool for organizing behavior. When interacting in person, people "interpret others' [social] locations through their bodies' appearance and perceived abilities" (Barrett 2022, p. 223). For young women, the physical co-presence of on-site work may heighten the risk of experiencing everyday gender discrimination. Studying young women's reports of discrimination, Duncan and Loretto (2004, p. 107) find that "one overarching ... [theme] was that many of the accounts of ageism provided by women contained a sexualized element." Although young women have the potential to experience sexualized treatment in both on-site and remote locations—for instance, receiving unwanted comments on-site or unwanted photos remotely—the possibility is greater on-site as a result of heightened gender salience during in-person interactions.

Of course, other individual characteristics may heighten gender salience, as well. For instance, others might view women as more or less stereotypically female based on their marital status, managerial authority, or organizational tenure. Yet as compared to age—which is communicated readily through bodily presence and presentation—these individual characteristics are less physically embodied. Because we are concerned with how characteristics amplify gender salience through in-person interactions, we

¹ Older women also experience uniquely gendered treatment in the workplace as well, including not being promoted to senior roles at the same rates as their same-aged male peers (Itzin and Phillipson 1995) and facing less sexual harassment than younger women (Walker and Zelin 2021). As compared to the gendered behaviors associated with youth, factors like lower promotion rates to senior roles and reduced instances of sexual harassment would not contribute to the kinds of everyday gender discrimination examined in this study.

focus on age as a trait that is particularly likely to telegraph gender on-site, and thus promote everyday gender discrimination.²

Given these arguments, we anticipate that young women, as compared to older women, will experience a more pronounced difference in the likelihood of experiencing discrimination between on-site and remote work. When on-site, colleagues and clients receive stronger social cues that saliently signal youth and gender through in-person interactions, potentially activating youth-gender stereotypes and discriminatory behaviors. In contrast, when working remotely, colleagues and clients receive relatively weaker social cues signaling youth and gender and would be less likely to engage in discriminatory behaviors. Because the difference in gender salience between on-site and remote work is likely to be somewhat less pronounced for older women, so too should the difference in their experiences of discrimination between the two locations. Specifically, we expect:

Hypothesis 2: The reduction in everyday gender discrimination associated with remote versus on-site work will be greater for younger women, compared to older women.

Contextual Moderator: Gender Composition of Interaction Partners

Alongside individual factors, contextual factors can also amplify gender salience (Ridgeway 2011). Existing research on gender and workplace interactions suggests that the gender composition of women's interaction partners can powerfully shape gender salience (Bobbitt-Zeher 2011, Kanter 1977, Qian and Fan 2019). Women interact with a set of individuals to complete their work, and that set has a certain gender composition. For example, a woman might interact with women only, men only, or a mix of women and men. We focus on the gender composition of women's interaction partners—rather than the gender-typing of their occupation or industry—because the immediacy of interactions has the potential to heighten gendered cues. Although one's occupation or industry provides an overall social framework that

² We nevertheless checked for marital status, managerial authority, as organizational tenure factors that might moderate the effect of location, although we find less theoretical motivation for such interactions. Consistent with expectations, these factors did not significantly moderate the effect of location on the likelihood of experiencing everyday gender discrimination.

diffusely shapes expectations and behaviors, direct communication and engagement with interaction partners are more likely to translate into heightened gender salience and the kinds of interaction-based everyday discrimination that constitute the focus of our study.

Existing research suggests that the gender frame is particularly salient when women interact with all or mostly men at work. When women are under-represented relative to men, gender becomes a powerful cultural frame for coordinating behavior (Ridgeway 2011). Classic research by Kanter (1977) shows that gender becomes highly salient at work when women are in the minority. Because women are more visible in male-dominated groups, male colleagues are more likely to scrutinize women's behavior and rely on gender stereotypes to guide their interactions with and expectations of women. Studies of workplace discrimination often conclude that women are most vulnerable to discrimination in settings dominated by men (Bobbitt-Zeher 2011, Burstein 1989). Indeed, women report more "unpleasantness" at work as the gender composition of their colleagues becomes increasingly male (Qian and Fan 2019).

There is good reason to suspect that gender salience would be particularly pronounced on-site among women who interact with all or mostly men. The heightened nonverbal features of communication that characterize on-site interactions are likely to highlight women's out-group position relative to their male interaction partners, fueling gender-stereotypical expectations and behaviors. As Ridgeway and Smith-Lovin (1999, p. 200) observe, "These often unconscious performance expectations shape behavior in a self-fulfilling way. They affect the likelihood that a man, compared to a woman, will speak up and make suggestions to the group and that others will respond positively to those suggestions, ask for the person's opinions, and accept influence from the person." Indeed, the nonverbal cues associated with in-person interactions are integral to gendered social categorization (Freeman et al. 2010, Lick and Johnson 2014) and are particularly important in maintaining gendered boundaries in male-dominated groups (Kanter 1977, Rasmussen 2005). In on-site work—where women's out-group status is telegraphed through nonverbal cues and physical features—in-person interactions serve to "continually refresh gender status beliefs" (Ridgeway and Smith-Lovin 1999, p. 209) and reinforce discriminatory tendencies.

Based on this research, we expect that women working predominantly with men will experience the most significant reductions in discrimination when working remotely. When on-site, the gender of these women is particularly salient, increasing the likelihood of gender discrimination; when remote, their gender should be far less salient, leading to a marked decrease in discrimination likelihood between the two settings. In other words, women who interact with more men stand to benefit considerably from the reduction of gender salience associated with remote work.

In contrast, women who work primarily with other women are likely to experience relatively less gender salience on-site and thus less of a difference between on-site and remote work. Women, compared to men, tend to hold less rigid stereotypes and expectations about other women (Parker and Funk 2017) and often evaluate other women's work more favorably (Özgümüs et al. 2020). Consequently, women who have more female interaction partners are likely to have less room for noticeable improvement in their everyday gendered experiences and should thus experience more modest differences in discrimination between on-site and remote work. Therefore, we expect:

Hypothesis 3: The reduction in everyday gender discrimination associated with remote versus on-site work will be greater for women who interact with all or mostly men, compared to those who interact with more women.

METHODS

Measuring Everyday Gender Discrimination

Capturing women's experiences of everyday gender discrimination requires presenting survey respondents with a list of discriminatory experiences that they might have had in remote or on-site work. To our knowledge, no such list exists. Thus, we developed and validated an inventory of everyday gender discrimination experiences.

We began by consulting the literature on gender discrimination. For example, we took inspiration from the 2017 Pew Research survey of workplace gender discrimination (Parker and Funk 2017) to craft items related to undermining women's competence. We also drew on sexual harassment surveys (i.e.,

Klonoff and Landrine 1995). Additionally, we rounded out our items by comparing them against Lamont et al.'s (2016) examples of “assaults on worth” as well as measures of everyday racial discrimination (Williams et al. 1997). Based on these and other studies, we created an initial list of nine types of everyday gender discrimination.

Recognizing that we had likely overlooked some forms of everyday gender discrimination, we surveyed 163 full-time workers (Supplemental Survey A) in the United States on Prolific to solicit feedback about the initial list.³ We first asked participants whether they had experienced each form of discrimination listed in Appendix Table A in the past month. Then we wrote, “We are currently developing these questions for a later survey. We would appreciate any feedback you have to improve the survey questions. Thinking about your own work experience, what types of everyday gender discrimination have you experienced that are not captured in the questions above? Please describe them here.” Participants could respond in an open-text box.

Respondents’ feedback helped expand and sharpen our list. Among respondents, 18% left the box blank and 61% indicated that the list was comprehensive. However, 20% (33 respondents) suggested experiences not captured in our list. For example, some respondents noted that colleagues had questioned their commitment to their jobs because of gendered responsibilities. One respondent wrote, “Judgment for taking sick days/parental leave/needng accommodations to account for childcare. This can be seen as not caring about work somehow, and that burden normally falls upon women.” In response to such comments, we added a new item: “Colleagues or clients make negative assumptions about your commitment to your job because of your gender.”

Finally, we revised the list to ensure that each experience could occur both on-site and remotely and that they reflected contemporary descriptions of gender discrimination (e.g., Robinson 2021, Tulshyan 2021). Table 1 contains the final list of 11 types of everyday gender discrimination. It includes

³ Respondents in Supplemental Survey A worked full- or part-time in professional roles across 18 industry sectors and 35 U.S. states. Respondents were 34.2 years old on average, and the modal respondent had 2-5 years experience in her current organization. Respondents worked in hybrid arrangements, fully remotely, or fully on-site.

examples of how each experience might unfold in remote and on-site contexts, drawing on survey respondents' open-ended descriptions of their personal experiences.

[Insert Table 1 about here.]

In developing this measure, we strove to generate a comprehensive roster of everyday gender discrimination that women might experience in remote or on-site work.⁴ Each experience in our list has the possibility of occurring in *either* location, though some forms of discrimination might occur more readily in one site or another. For example, colleagues might be more inclined to share jokes remotely or to exclude women from activities on-site. Usefully, our measure of everyday gender discrimination allows us to capture such potential variation, while still facilitating an analysis of which location is associated with more discrimination overall. To that end, we aimed to develop a complete measure, ensuring that we did not overlook important experiences whose exclusion would skew our understanding of where discrimination occurs.

By design, our measure captures self-reports, which are important for several reasons. First, they provide insight into perceptions of discrimination. Individuals suffer a host of negative consequences when they believe they have been discriminated against or treated unfairly at work, including lower job satisfaction (Ensher et al. 2001), reduced performance (Masterson et al. 2000), as well as negative physical and mental health outcomes (Williams et al. 2008). Second, perceived discrimination is highly consequential for organizations. Employees who believe they were the targets of discrimination have higher turnover intentions (Madera et al. 2012) and “naming” an event as discriminatory is a necessary step towards taking legal action (Felstiner et al. 1981, Hirsh and Lyons 2010). Both outcomes—employee turnover and legal claims—are costly for organizations (Glebbeck and Bax 2004, Goldman et al. 2006). Finally, our focus on perceived discrimination responds to calls in the literature to investigate the subjective nature of discrimination (Bielby 2000, Doering et al. 2023, Hart 2021, Small and Pager 2020, Sue 2010), thereby providing a clearer picture of how workers experience it.

⁴ In the Discussion, we consider how experiences that could only occur in a single location might influence our understanding of everyday gender discrimination.

Sample and Procedures

To examine women's experiences with everyday gender discrimination, we surveyed a purposive sample of women who work in the same white-collar jobs remotely and on-site. For example, a respondent might work as an associate at a law firm, spending three days a week working from home and two days a week at the office. We focused on women who work in the same job in different locations to hold constant time-invariant individual characteristics across settings. Each respondent in our study has two distinct sets of observations: one for remote work and one for on-site work. This design allows us to compare individuals to themselves, holding constant factors that might otherwise affect gender discrimination but are invariant across locations, such as socioeconomic status, prior experiences, current job, and organization. Controlling for such factors allows us to more precisely estimate the relationship between work location and everyday gender discrimination.

Our survey aimed to analyze within-gender differences to understand how work location affects women's experiences of gender discrimination. We opted for this approach—rather than a between-gender analysis comparing women to men—for two reasons. First, we were guided by research emphasizing that within-group analyses are particularly valuable when the focal group (in our case, women) experiences an outcome of interest fundamentally differently than the dominant group (i.e., men) (Dennis 2021, Stewart 2008, see also Kessler-Harris 2003). In adopting this approach, we follow numerous studies of women in the workplace analyzing within-gender differences, rather than contrasting women's experiences against men's (e.g., Byrne and Barling 2017, England et al. 2016, Gangl and Ziefle 2015, Melin and Correll 2022, Trzebiatowski et al. 2023, Yang et al. 2023). Second, our decision to focus on women was further motivated by prior research emphasizing the appropriateness of within-group analyses when the focal group experiences the outcome of interest at higher rates than the dominant group (Dennis 2021, Stewart 2008). Based on prior studies (e.g., Parker and Funk 2017), we anticipated that men would report lower rates of gender discrimination in both settings. We confirmed this expectation in

a small survey (Supplemental Survey B, $N = 299$), finding that only a small fraction of men reported experiencing gender discrimination remotely or on-site.⁵

To conduct our main survey, we used the Prolific platform to solicit responses from professional women with hybrid work arrangements. We detail the recruitment strategy in Appendix A. We made the survey available to women aged 18-75, in the United States, who indicated that they worked in professional roles,⁶ restricting invitations to those who had hybrid arrangements in the past month. In total, we collected 1,091 complete responses. The median and modal respondent split her time evenly between locations, with 50% of time spent on-site.

We took several steps to ensure validity. First, we used the Prolific platform, where participants tend to be relatively attentive and engaged (Peer et al. 2017). Second, we used demographic screening measures to ensure that respondents resided in the U.S. and were over 18 years old. Because respondents report these characteristics when they join the platform, they cannot change or misrepresent them to participate in a particular study (Palan and Schitter 2018). Third, we included two attention checks to screen out inattentive respondents. The data, code, and survey instrument are available at <https://doi.org/10.5683/SP3/TMIDWR>.

Analytic Strategy

We measure whether women experience more everyday gender discrimination in remote or on-site work, as well as the conditions that moderate such location-based differences. Each participant in our study has two observations: one set of responses for remote work and one set for on-site work. For instance, respondents might indicate that they experienced a particular form of everyday discrimination remotely, but not on-site. Our survey is unique in that it allows participants to indicate how their experiences and work conditions may differ in each location and incorporates these differences into the analyses. We use

⁵ Respondents in Supplemental Survey B worked full- or part-time in professional roles in the United States. All respondents had hybrid work arrangements. On average, respondents were 38.6 years old and spent 51% of their time on-site.

⁶ Professional roles include the following categories: upper management, middle management, junior management, trained professional, consultant, researcher, self-employed/partner, support staff, or administrative staff.

linear probability fixed-effects models to estimate the relationship between work location and everyday gender discrimination. The fixed-effects approach is well-suited to our within-subject design, in which each participant has one remote work observation and one on-site observation (Allison 2009). Including individual fixed effects allows us to hold constant location-invariant factors that might shape discrimination experiences (e.g., socioeconomic status, personality traits, and organizational characteristics). We use a linear probability model because it is well-suited to modeling dichotomous outcomes (Hellevik 2009), particularly when including fixed effects. Compared to fixed-effects logistic regressions—which require individual-level variation on the dependent variable—the linear probability model incorporates data from respondents who report discrimination in both locations, just one location, or neither location.

We demonstrate the consistency of our findings by using logistic regression analyses with standard errors clustered by individuals (an approach that does not include fixed effects). These models account for the non-independence of remote and on-site locations through clustered standard errors (Abadie et al. 2017) and allow us to examine the main effects of location-invariant controls (e.g., organization size, managerial role, etc.) on discrimination. These secondary models supplement our more conservative fixed-effects analyses.

Everyday Gender Discrimination, Location, and Moderators

Our outcome variable captures whether or not women experienced everyday gender discrimination. Survey participants indicated whether they experienced each type of discrimination listed in Table 1 in the past month, with experiences appearing in random order. If a participant affirmed that she had a particular experience, she then indicated whether it occurred when she was working remotely, on-site, or in both locations. Following other studies of gender discrimination (e.g., Parker and Funk 2017, Roscigno et al. 2021), we created a binary variable to capture whether participants did or did not experience any form of everyday gender discrimination in the past month. Of respondents, 34% affirmed that they experienced some form of everyday gender discrimination, with 10% reporting one experience, 8% reporting two, 5%

reporting three, and 11% reporting four or more. Although our models use a binary outcome, we find consistent results when predicting the total number of discrimination experiences.

Our main predictor variable is work location. The variable *remote location* indicates whether the focal observation corresponds to remote or on-site work (remote = 1, on-site = 0). Next, we include our hypothesized moderators. We examine whether age moderates the effect of location on discrimination experiences using the variable *age under 30*. We follow prior research on the intersection of gender, age and workplace discrimination to define “young” as being under 30 (Duncan and Loretto 2004, Gander 2014, Mengel et al. 2019), but results are consistent at higher and lower age cutoffs. To measure the *gender of interaction partners*, we asked, “When working [on-site/remotely], do you interact with mostly women, mostly men, or men and women equally?” Participants indicated the gender composition of their interaction partners on a five-point Likert-style scale ranging from only or mostly women to only or mostly men.

Location-Variant Control Variables

In our fixed-effects models, we control for factors that may vary by location. For these variables, we asked women to indicate location-specific responses. One variable that might differ by location is monitoring frequency. Monitoring refers to the “observation, examination and/or recording of employee work-related behaviors” (Stanton 2000, p. 87). Employees often align their behavior with organizational expectations when under observation (Bernstein 2012), suggesting that monitoring might deter workers from engaging in everyday gender discrimination. To account for this possibility, we asked, “When working [on-site/remotely], how often are your and your co-workers’ behaviors and interactions observed, examined, and/or recorded, with or without technological assistance, by your supervisor or someone else in the organization?” Participants indicated the level of monitoring they experienced in each location on a five-point Likert-style scale ranging from very frequently to never. For ease of interpretation, we collapsed responses into a binary outcome, with *high monitoring* = 1 for “very frequently” or “often” and 0 otherwise. Nevertheless, our analyses are robust to including all monitoring

categories. In the Robustness Checks and Additional Analysis section, we examine monitoring frequencies by location and consider their implications.

Next, we controlled for *frequent formal interactions* and *frequent informal interactions* in the workplace, which can vary by location. More frequent interactions may increase the likelihood of experiencing discrimination (Homans 1950, Simmel 1971). We include separate measures of formal and informal interactions because each type of interaction may be associated with different kinds of discrimination. We measured interaction frequency by asking, “When working [on-site/remotely], how often do you [formally/informally] interact with colleagues, clients, or supervisors?” Participants indicated interaction frequency in each location on a five-point Likert-style scale ranging from very frequently to never. For ease of interpretation, we collapsed these responses into a binary variable, where *frequent [formal/informal] interactions* equals 1 for “very frequently” or “often” and 0 otherwise. Our analyses are robust to including all interaction frequency categories.

Location-Constant Control Variables in Secondary Analyses

Our supplemental, between-individual analyses control for factors that do not vary by location. Because these variables are constant across locations, they are dropped from the fixed-effects analyses.

One such location-constant factor is being a *manager*, defined as holding an upper, middle, or junior managerial role. When occupying positions of authority, female managers violate the prescriptive gender stereotypes that women should be compliant and lower-status, rather than directive and higher-status (Prentice and Carranza 2002, Rudman and Glick 2001). By violating these gender stereotypes—as well as occupying high-visibility positions—female managers may be more vulnerable to everyday gender discrimination.

To account for differences in the amount of time respondents spend remotely or on-site, we controlled for the *percentage of time spent on-site*. Women in our sample split their time relatively evenly between remote and on-site work. On average, women spent 52% of their time on-site (median = 50%),

and 50% was the modal response. This relative balance between locations facilitates our analyses because women on average had similar exposure to potential discrimination in each context.

We also accounted for personal characteristics that may affect gender discrimination. In some contexts, women of color report more gender discrimination than white women (Roscigno 2007). We thus control for race (*white* = 1; other = 0). Additionally, women's marital and motherhood statuses may affect their likelihood of experiencing some forms of gender discrimination (Acker 1990, Heilman 2001, Schultz 2016). We thus controlled for whether a respondent was *married* and whether she was a *mother*. Because more educated women tend to report more gender discrimination (Parker and Funk 2017), we also control for *university education* (bachelor's degree or higher).

Additionally, large organizations often have more sophisticated anti-discrimination policies (Dobbin et al. 2007). Thus, we controlled for working in an *organization with > 1000 employees*, a common cut point for "large" organizations in the United States (e.g., U.S Bureau of Labor Statistics 2023). Finally, we controlled for being a *part-time worker*. Part-time workers may have less exposure to discrimination since they spend less time at work, but they also tend to have lower organizational status, potentially making them more vulnerable to discrimination (McDonald et al. 2009, Tomlinson 2006).

RESULTS

Descriptive Results: More Everyday Gender Discrimination On-Site

Respondents came from 48 states, 17 industry sectors, and nine types of work roles. While our sample comprises women with diverse work experiences, the modal respondent worked in a large organization with 5,000 or more employees—most often a for-profit company. The modal respondent was a "trained professional" with a bachelor's degree, had a direct supervisor, and had worked at her organization for at least five years. Among respondents, 44% were managers and 31% engaged in customer- or client-facing work. The majority (87%) worked full-time. They divided that time nearly evenly between remote and on-site work; the average respondent spent 52% of her time working on-site (median = 50%).

Notably, survey respondents have characteristics that parallel the broader population of U.S. hybrid workers. Like our sample, hybrid workers tend to be knowledge or professional service workers, and they are found most commonly in large firms (Barrero et al. 2023). Hybrid workers' tasks tend to be analytic and computer-intensive, making their work portable across locations (ibid). This portability of tasks suggests that participants in our sample should be able to execute many of their core tasks both remotely and on-site. Further, research indicates that hybrid work is most pervasive among more educated, white-collar workers (Barrero et al. 2023, Garrote Sanchez et al. 2021), consistent with our decision to recruit professionals for our main survey.

In our sample, respondents were 39 years old on average (median = 36). Younger women (under 30) and older women split their time similarly between on-site and remote work. On average, younger women spent 54% of their time on-site and older women spent 51% on-site. In reporting their interaction partners at work, respondents on average fell between working with slightly more women than men, and men and women equally. As shown in Figure 1, the distribution of the gender composition of interaction partners was similar in on-site and remote work. Women across gender composition categories also split their time similarly evenly across locations. On average, those who interact with only or mostly women spent 53% of their time on-site, and those who work with only or mostly men spent 48% of their time on-site; all other groups fell between those values.

[Insert Figure 1 about here.]

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics and the correlation matrix. Because each of the 1,091 survey respondents has two unique observations (one for remote work, one for on-site work), the total number of observations is 2,182.

[Insert Table 2 about here.]

In the prior month, 34% of respondents experienced some form of everyday gender discrimination. This value aligns with previous surveys. For instance, in a nationally representative survey from Pew Research, 42% of women report that they have at some point experienced gender

discrimination at work (Parker and Funk 2017).⁷ In our sample, women were more likely to report experiencing everyday gender discrimination on-site versus remotely (31% versus 17%, $z = 7.49$, $p < .001$). Figure 2 presents values for each type of everyday gender discrimination, showing higher on-site percentages for all experiences. Tests of proportions confirm that—across each type of everyday gender discrimination—significantly higher proportions of women report discrimination on-site, as compared to remotely. For example, 9% of women report personality-related gender discrimination on-site, compared to 4% remotely ($z = 4.83$, $p < .001$). And 14% of respondents said they had been underestimated because of their gender on-site, whereas only 6% said the same occurred remotely ($z = 5.73$, $p < .001$).⁸ In a separate analysis, we found that the tendency for women to report more everyday gender discrimination on-site is consistent regardless of the type of person they interact with most frequently (i.e., colleagues, clients, direct reports, or supervisors).

[Insert Figure 2 about here.]

As an additional check and a point of comparison, we asked respondents to answer questions about gender discrimination that were used in prior studies. We found that—consistent with our measure of everyday gender discrimination—respondents reported significantly more gender discrimination on-site versus remotely. Responding to gender discrimination questions drawn in the General Social Survey (GSS 2018), 16% of our survey respondents indicated on-site discrimination versus 7% remotely ($z = 6.22$, $p < .001$). Responding to questions about gender-based incivility from the Workplace Incivility Scale (Cortina et al. 2001), 27% indicated incivility on-site versus 14% remotely ($z = 7.76$, $p < .001$).⁹

⁷ This value is likely higher than what our respondents report because the Pew survey 1) includes in the definition of gender discrimination experiences that would fall outside everyday gender discrimination (like earning less than a man) and 2) does not specify a time period, whereas we ask respondents to report experiences from the past month only.

⁸ One might wonder whether women in lower-level roles are more likely to be asked to perform tasks unrelated to their jobs, given their lower organizational status. Contrary to this expectation, we find that women in higher-level roles are more likely to report being asked to perform unrelated tasks. For example, 13% of managers report being asked to perform unrelated tasks on-site, compared to 7% of non-managers ($z = -3.01$, $p < .01$). The same trends hold in remote work. Thus, this tendency does not appear to be driven by colleagues and clients asking lower-level workers to perform unrelated tasks.

⁹ The percentage of respondents affirming incivility and everyday gender discrimination is higher than that of GSS discrimination because the former two measures contain a series of items related to specific experiences, whereas the GSS item consists of two simple, broad questions that may not elicit the same level of recall.

Results from these alternative measures confirm our basic finding: women report having more negative gendered experiences on-site as compared to remotely.

Predicting Everyday Gender Discrimination in Remote and On-site Work

Table 3 presents regression models of the relationship between location and discrimination. Model 1 is a linear probability fixed-effects model, which compares individuals to themselves in remote and on-site work, thereby holding constant location-invariant characteristics. It shows that women experience significantly less gender discrimination remotely than on-site (Model 1: $\beta = -0.11, p < .001$). Using predicted probabilities with mean-constant controls, we find that in a one-month period, 18% of women are predicted to experience everyday gender discrimination remotely, as compared with 29% on-site.

Model 2 demonstrates the consistency of these results using a between-individual logistic regression with standard errors clustered by individuals. Again, we find that women report significantly less everyday gender discrimination remotely compared to on-site (Model 2: $\beta = -0.73, p < .001$). Based on this model, 16% of women are predicted to experience everyday gender discrimination remotely in a given month, compared to 28% on-site. Model 2 shows that women are significantly less likely to experience everyday gender discrimination remotely, even when controlling for a battery of factors, like being a manager, percentage of time spent on-site, and organizational size.

[Insert Table 3 about here.]

The control variables offer additional insights. Consistent with prior research (e.g., Bobbitt-Zeher 2011), women report more discrimination when they work with more men. Women in managerial roles also report higher levels of discrimination, perhaps due to a backlash against women in positions of authority (e.g., Rudman and Glick 2001). The effect of high monitoring on gender discrimination depends on model specification; we offer an interpretation of these findings in the Robustness Checks and Additional Analysis section.

In that section, we also confirm that these effects are not driven by 1) women who perform different tasks remotely and on-site; 2) women who determine when they work remotely and on-site; 3) women who spend small proportions of time working remotely; or 4) women who have an expressed preference for remote work. Across all models, the results consistently demonstrate that women experience less gender discrimination when they work remotely versus on-site.

Age

Do young women experience a more pronounced reduction in discrimination when working remotely, compared to older women? Table 4 presents the results of the analysis testing this possibility. Model 1 is a fixed-effects linear probability model, and Model 2 is a logistic regression analysis with standard errors clustered by individuals. Although the main effects of location-invariant variables are absorbed by the fixed effects in Model 1, they can be interacted with factors that vary by location (Allison 2009); this allows us to interact age with location. Model 1 in Table 4 shows a significant, negative interaction coefficient (Model 1: $\beta = -0.06, p < .05$) and Model 2 offers consistent results ($\beta = -0.43, p < .05$).

[Insert Table 4 about here.]

Figure 3 shows women's predicted probability of experiencing gender discrimination in on-site and remote work. First, we note that younger women are more likely to report gender discrimination on-site than older women (31% versus 26%), consistent with our expectation that young women will experience more pronounced gender salience on-site. Next, we find that the difference in discrimination likelihood between on-site and remote work is greater for younger women, whose likelihood of experiencing discrimination drops from 31% on-site to 14% remotely. Among those over 30, the difference is narrower, with 26% predicted to experience discrimination on-site versus 16% remotely. These findings support Hypothesis 2.

[Insert Figure 3 about here.]

We probed the sensitivity of these results by asking: do younger and older women experience different levels of location-based discrimination because they split their time differently between locations? In particular, do young women experience more on-site discrimination because they spend more time on-site? Thus far, we accounted for this possibility by presenting descriptive statistics showing that younger and older women split their time similarly between locations, by including individual fixed-effects that account for time splits, and by including the *percentage of time on-site* as a control in Model 2. To further test this possibility, we ran an additional analysis that included the interaction term *remote location X percentage of time on-site* in Model 1. If our moderating effects could be explained by younger and older women splitting their time differently between locations, then adding this interaction term to Model 1 would result in a non-significant interaction of *remote location X age under 30*. However, even when including the additional interaction term, the interaction for *remote location X age under 30* remains negative and significant. This test provides increased confidence that differences in time spent on-site among younger and older women do not drive the observed moderating influence of age. In Appendix B, we discuss descriptive results showing that younger and older women experience similar types of everyday gender discrimination in remote and on-site work.

Gender of Interaction Partners

Do women who interact with all or mostly men experience a greater reduction in everyday gender discrimination in remote work, compared to women who interact with more women? In Model 1 of Table 4, we test whether the gender composition of respondents' interaction partners in on-site and remote work moderates the effect of location on gender discrimination. We find a significant, negative interaction coefficient for three gender composition categories (*men and women equally, slightly more men, only or mostly men*), as compared to the reference category (*only or mostly women*). In Model 2, which serves as a confirmatory check, we find a significant, negative interaction of location and women who work with *only or mostly men*.

[Insert Figure 4 about here.]

Figure 4 presents the predicted probabilities of experiencing everyday gender discrimination with all controls constant at their means. Women who work with only or mostly women have similar predicted probabilities of everyday gender discrimination by location: 14% on-site versus 12% remotely. But as the interaction partners include more men, the difference in predicted probabilities expands, with the largest gap among those who work with only or mostly men: 58% on-site versus 26% remotely. The difference in the predicted probability of experiencing everyday gender discrimination is greatest for women who work with only or mostly men, whose likelihood of on-site discrimination is also higher than that of women who work with only or mostly women (58% versus 14%). These findings align with our expectations in hypothesis 3 that on-site gender salience is heightened among women who interact with more men and that those women stand to benefit more from the reduction of gender salience associated with remote work.

We confirmed these results with two sensitivity analyses. As above, we considered whether differences in time spent on-site might drive location-based differences in discrimination. The main concern is that women who work with only or mostly men may spend more time on-site, potentially fueling their likelihood of experiencing on-site discrimination. Although descriptive statistics show that women across these groups split their time similarly evenly across locations, and both models account for time splits, we tested this possibility further by adding to Model 1 the interaction term *remote location X percentage of time spent on-site*. When including this term, the interaction of location by gender composition remained negative and significant at the same levels as Model 1, suggesting that the results are not driven by the amount of time that women spend working on-site. Additionally, we tested whether the results might be driven by the gender composition of women's industry sectors. In particular, we considered whether working in a male-dominated industry might drive the results. To test this possibility, we included an interaction for *remote location X male-dominated industry* and found that it did not alter the significance or directionality of the results. These tests provide further confidence that it is primarily the gender composition of women's set of interaction partners—and not time spent on-site or working in a

male-dominant industry—that shapes their likelihood of experiencing everyday gender discrimination in remote versus on-site work. In Appendix B, we discuss descriptive results showing that women tend to experience similar types of everyday gender discrimination in remote and on-site work, regardless of the gender of their interaction partners.

Robustness Checks and Additional Analyses

Task Similarity, Determining Work Location, and Time Spent On-site

One empirical concern about our main effect relates to differences in the types of work performed remotely and on-site. Although we have accounted for how women’s formal and informal interaction frequency differs by location, it is possible that women perform different tasks in each location in ways that make them more susceptible to gender discrimination on-site. To examine this possibility, we re-ran our baseline models on the subset of women who indicated that the tasks they perform remotely and on-site are “completely similar.” As with prior models, we find that women who perform completely similar tasks in each location are nevertheless significantly less likely to experience everyday gender discrimination remotely versus on-site. We present these results in the online supplement (Table B, Model 1). In additional models, we have found that the frequency of everyday gender discrimination is significantly lower in remote work than in on-site work in every subsample defined by the level of task similarity (i.e., those with not at all similar tasks, slightly similar tasks, somewhat similar tasks, mostly similar tasks, or completely similar tasks).

A second issue is control over one’s remote and on-site work arrangements. Women who are able to determine when they work remotely or on-site may use this flexibility strategically to make everyday gender discrimination less likely in remote contexts. For example, they might opt to work remotely on days when large meetings occur and they anticipate experiencing discrimination. To account for this possibility, we re-ran the baseline analyses on the sample of respondents who reported that “someone else” (not themselves) determines their work location. Although these individuals cannot strategically

avoid location-based discrimination, they are nevertheless significantly less likely to experience everyday gender discrimination remotely. We present the results in the online supplement (Table B).

An additional concern relates to the amount of time that women spend working remotely versus on-site. Although we controlled for the percentage of time spent on-site in our models, it is possible that women who spend most of their time working on-site nevertheless drive our results. To rule out this possibility, we re-ran the baseline analysis on women who spend 50% or less of their time on-site. This subsample skews our results toward women who spend most of their time working remotely and thus have the most opportunity to experience gender discrimination remotely. Yet even under these conservative specifications, we find that women are significantly less likely to experience gender discrimination remotely versus on-site (Table B). The consistency of effects across these subsamples reinforces our core finding: remote work is associated with significantly less everyday gender discrimination among professional women.

Under- and Over-reporting of Everyday Gender Discrimination

A different concern pertains to participants' reporting motivations. If survey participants prefer to work remotely for reasons unrelated to everyday gender discrimination—such as flexibility or the lack of a commute—they may be motivated to underreport discrimination in remote work or overreport it in on-site work. To address this concern, we administered to a subsample of our participants ($N = 610$) a brief supplemental survey (Supplemental Survey C, detailed in Appendix C of the online supplement) in which they rated the extent to which they preferred remote versus on-site work.¹⁰

If motivated under- or over-reporting drove our results, we would observe that participants with a general preference for remote work report particularly low levels of discrimination in remote work or particularly high levels of discrimination in on-site work. We would also find that the greater likelihood of

¹⁰ Respondents in Supplemental Survey C worked full- or part-time in professional roles across 17 industry sectors and 47 U.S. states. On average, respondents were 39.9 years old and spent 51.9% of their time on-site. The modal respondent had five or more years experience in their current organization.

everyday gender discrimination in on-site compared to remote work is (a) particularly pronounced among those who favor remote work and (b) less evident among those who do *not* prefer remote work.

However, we find no evidence for such patterns, which suggests that motivated under- and over-reporting does not confound our main findings. First, our item measuring preference for remote work is essentially uncorrelated with reported everyday gender discrimination on-site ($r = 0.03$) and remotely ($r = 0.03$). Thus, a general preference for remote work does not predict reporting more everyday gender discrimination on-site or less everyday gender discrimination remotely. Second, when we regress everyday gender discrimination on (a) location, (b) preference for remote work, and (c) their interaction, the coefficient of the interaction term is negligibly small and not statistically significant ($p = .997$). Thus, we find no evidence that participants with a strong preference for remote work are driving our results.

Third, if we narrow the sample to participants who prefer on-site arrangements or are indifferent between remote and on-site work—that is, respondents who should *not* be motivated to underreport discrimination in remote work or to overreport it in on-site work—we still find results consistent with our main findings. In this subsample ($N = 142$), 32% of participants reported everyday gender discrimination on-site and 18% reported it in remote work, a difference of 14 percentage points ($z = 2.60, p < .01$). These results closely mirror our overall findings (31% on-site versus 17% remotely). Overall, we find no evidence that our findings reflect tendentious reporting of everyday gender discrimination due to a general preference for remote work.

Monitoring

Monitoring—which refers to the “observation, examination and/or recording of employee work-related behaviors” (Stanton 2000, p. 87)—has the potential to influence everyday gender discrimination. When employees know they are being observed, they are more likely to align their behavior with organizational expectations (Bernstein 2012). Because many organizations have anti-discrimination policies, monitoring may dissuade workers from engaging in everyday gender discrimination.

We explored whether locational differences in monitoring might offer further insights into the reduced gender discrimination we observe in remote work. In particular, we examined whether respondents reported higher levels of monitoring in remote or on-site locations. One might expect that workers experience more monitoring remotely given that communication tools associated with remote work are often recorded (Leonardi 2021), leaving digital “traces” (Yoo et al. 2012). However, on-site work also has the potential for high monitoring because individuals can easily be observed and tracked (Ajunwa et al. 2017), especially in shared spaces (Chen 2018, Laurence et al. 2013). When on-site, employees are “subject to monitoring, including office and cubicle searches, video surveillance, [and technologies that] greatly enhanc[e] employers’ ability to keep tabs on employees and [...] monitor virtually every aspect of a worker’s activities” (Wilborn 1997, p. 826).

In our survey, respondents reported similar levels of monitoring in each location, with slightly more monitoring on-site. Figure 5 shows how often respondents reported being monitored on-site and remotely; notably, a smaller percentage of respondents indicated that they were “never” monitored on-site, compared to remotely (24% on-site versus 32% remotely; $z = -4.26, p < .001$), suggesting more on-site monitoring. Thus, it does not appear that higher monitoring frequency is a unique characteristic of remote work that would help explain reduced gender discrimination in that setting.

[Insert Figure 5 about here.]

Our monitoring-related findings in Table 3 also warrant consideration. There, the between-individual analysis shows a significant, positive relationship between monitoring and everyday gender discrimination (Model 2: $\beta = 0.59, p < .001$), whereas our within-individual fixed-effects analysis shows no discernible relationship (Model 1: $\beta = 0.01, p = .689$). We suspect that the positive relationship in Model 2 reflects between-organizational differences. Model 2 is a logistic regression that does not hold constant unobserved location-invariant factors. In such an analysis, the observed relationship between monitoring and discrimination could be complicated by the possibility that organizations implement monitoring practices *in response* to discrimination complaints (e.g., Conger 2019, Liao 2022). Just as

police install cameras in high-crime areas (Vlahos 2012), organizations with more discrimination complaints may monitor workers more frequently.

In Model 1, we find no significant effect of *high monitoring* on discrimination. Notably, this fixed-effects model compares within-individual (and thus within-organizational) differences. The non-significant effect suggests that when individuals switch from high- to low-monitoring environments (in the same organization), there is no discernible difference in the likelihood of experiencing everyday gender discrimination.

DISCUSSION

Organizational scholars have long studied how physical location affects employee experiences. A century ago, Max Weber (1923) highlighted how the physical relocation of workers from homes to factories marked a transformative shift in the Industrial Revolution. Weber recognized that the separation of a worker's dwelling from their place of work had profound economic and societal consequences. In contemporary times, the location of work has again shifted; technological advances have expanded workspaces to nearly any location, with many professionals now working fully or partially remotely. This surge in remote and hybrid work models constitutes one of the most fundamental changes to modern white-collar work (Bloom et al. 2022, Neeley 2021, Stephenson et al. 2020, Villamor et al. 2023).

Recent research has examined the myriad ways work location affects employees (Bloom et al. 2022, Bucher and Langley 2016, Gonsalves 2020, Kellogg 2009, Lee 2019). However, the effect of work location on everyday gender discrimination—a pressing issue for many workers—has remained largely unexplored. In this study, we examine the relationship between work location and self-reported experiences of everyday gender discrimination. In a survey of professional women in the U.S. who work in the same job both remotely and on-site, we find that women consistently report experiencing everyday gender discrimination more frequently on-site than when working remotely. In other words, remote work is strongly and consistently associated with reduced everyday gender discrimination. Although this

pattern persists across various work environments and individual worker characteristics, there is also evidence that remote work offers especially pronounced relief from gender discrimination for certain women. Younger women and those who interact mostly with men at work experience a particularly significant decrease in everyday gender discrimination when working remotely rather than on-site.

Taken together, these findings have implications for organizational research on work location and gender discrimination, the trade-offs of remote work for professional women, and the contextual factors shaping discrimination and inequality in the workplace.

Work Location and Gender Discrimination

While there is considerable scholarly interest in both gender discrimination (e.g., Fernandez-Mateo and Kaplan 2018, Quadlin 2018, Joshi et al. 2024) and the impact of work location on various employee outcomes (e.g., Barrero et al. 2023, Conzon 2023, Emanuel et al. 2023), scant research has addressed directly how work location influences gender discrimination. Informed by gender frame theory and the literature on gender, stereotypes, and virtual work, our study shows that remote work is consistently associated with fewer incidents of everyday gender discrimination. This pattern is not limited to a specific subset of workers or workplaces; it is widely observed across diverse settings and among various employees. Thus, remote work serves as a protective shield against everyday gender discrimination across a range of contexts and individual characteristics.

At the same time, the decrease in everyday gender discrimination due to remote work is most pronounced for younger women and those with more male interaction partners—situations where gender salience is particularly high on-site and less salient in remote work. While remote work provides a degree of protection against everyday gender discrimination across the board, the magnitude of its impact varies based on age and the gender composition of interaction partners. These findings offer an important advance upon the few surveys that have examined the relationship between work location and gender discrimination. To date, that limited research comes from industry surveys, which offer mixed results

(e.g., Hong et al. 2021, Thomas et al. 2022). Although these surveys have conflicting findings and serious empirical shortcomings, they often fuel hyperbolic media narratives. Our findings paint a more nuanced and complete picture. We find less everyday gender discrimination overall in remote work, but also show that not all women experience this effect equally. By demonstrating variation alongside overall effects, we draw attention to the intersectionality of gender and age as well as the interplay between location and the gender of interaction partners.

Overall, our findings are consistent with the literature on gender stereotypes and virtual work, especially the notion that virtual work settings tend to reduce social cues and thus lessen the salience of gender-related cues that often lead to stereotyping and discrimination on-site (see Bommer and Schmidtke 2022, Villamor et al. 2023). We have further developed this perspective by integrating it with gender frame theory (Ridgeway 1997, 2011, Ridgeway and Correll 2004). This synthesis makes it possible to formulate predictions not only about the overall effect of remote work on everyday gender discrimination but also about variation across individual and contextual factors.

The Trade-offs of Remote Work for Professional Women

Organizational scholars have begun to document the complex, multifaceted impact of virtual work on women's professional advancement, noting both its career-enhancing and career-damaging effects (Villamor et al. 2023). For instance, while virtual work arrangements offer women greater location flexibility, making it simpler to juggle non-work responsibilities, they also blur the boundary between work and family, intensifying family obligations, even during work hours, which might have ripple effects on women's careers (Coltrane 2004). Our study contributes to this literature by illuminating everyday gender discrimination as a critical factor in the complex gender dynamics of remote and on-site work. While recent research underscores the benefits of on-site work for women in receiving valuable feedback and mentorship (Emanuel et al. 2023) and leveraging their distinct managerial strengths (Conzon 2023),

our study reveals a concurrent gender discrimination penalty when women work on-site rather than remotely.

While this finding presents a tension that professional women must navigate, it also helps open a promising avenue for future research into the interplay between gender and work location. In particular, how do women navigate the advantages and disadvantages of different work locations? Presumably, many women are aware of the professional advantages that on-site work offers (Conzon 2023). How do women manage this trade-off? Exploring such questions can shift our focus from charting gendered experiences across work settings to uncovering the tactics that individual workers and managers adopt to optimize benefits and mitigate drawbacks inherent to each location.

Similar trade-offs exist at the organizational level as well, suggesting a complex relationship between work location and organizational performance. On the one hand, on-site work facilitates richer and faster communication (Battiston et al. 2021), reduces coordination costs (Gibbs et al. 2021), fosters more dynamically changing and less siloed collaboration networks (Yang et al. 2022), and contributes to long-term employee development and productivity (Emanuel et al. 2023). On the other hand, we find that on-site work is associated with a higher incidence of everyday gender discrimination, which previous research suggests may have a detrimental effect on psychological well-being and job performance (Smith and Griffiths 2022). Specifically, experiencing everyday discrimination might lead to lower job satisfaction, increased burnout, and decreased work performance (Hu et al. 2019, Smith and Griffiths 2022). Furthermore, women who experience everyday gender discrimination might feel less psychologically safe (e.g., He et al. 2023, Robinson et al. 2018), which can make it more difficult for them to take risks, propose new ideas, and voice concerns. This, in turn, can reduce work engagement, increase turnover intentions, and impair team learning and team performance in the long run (Carmeli et al. 2009, Edmondson 1999, Robinson 2018). Future research aimed at exploring how organizations navigate this trade-off is crucial for understanding the broader performance implications of remote versus on-site work.

Location as a Contextual Influence on Discrimination

Over the last three decades, organizational research has significantly advanced our understanding of workplace discrimination in its many forms. This vast literature has documented a wide range of institutional and situational factors that influence discrimination at work, including organizational, administrative, and legal practices as well as broader economic, demographic, and political conditions (e.g., Castilla 2015, Dobbin et al. 2015, Glick and Fiske 2007, Gorman 2005, Hirsh and Kornrich 2008, Kalev et al. 2006, Pager and Shepherd 2008, Quillian and Midtbøen 2021, Rivera 2020). However, this stream of research has not systematically examined how the location of work—on-site or remote—affects experiences of discrimination. We contribute to this literature by advancing a location-based perspective on workplace discrimination and highlighting the significance of on-site and remote work environments as crucial contextual elements influencing the incidence of everyday gender discrimination.

These findings also underscore recent calls from legal scholars to examine the role of location and space in discrimination. As Green (2021, p. 144) notes, “We are at a moment when people are more willing than ever to think about structures and systems in our calls for justice for women and people of color. Spatial features should be a prominent lever in that project.” Our research provides theoretical and empirical justification for pursuing such a location-sensitive approach to workplace discrimination.

Future work can push our findings forward by examining other ways that location shapes discrimination. For example, our study focuses on discrimination experiences that can occur both remotely and on-site in order to make cross-location comparisons. Yet future research could consider how location-specific experiences—like being asked to tidy up the office kitchen, which can only occur on-site—influence the distribution of everyday gender discrimination. Additionally, women’s experiences of gender discrimination may differ depending on whether they began their jobs in fully remote, fully on-site, or hybrid arrangements. Given the power of early experiences to pattern individuals’ long-term outcomes (Azoulay et al. 2017, Tilcsik 2014), researchers should examine how location-based imprinting may affect subsequent experiences of discrimination.

Study Limitations and Future Research

Like any study, this one has limitations that create possibilities for future research. One of the strengths of our research design is its focus on individuals' subjective perceptions of discrimination, which scholars have highlighted as an important and consequential axis of discrimination that demands further research (e.g., Bielby 2000, Hart 2021, Small and Pager 2020, Sue 2010). Perceived discrimination has been linked to a range of negative psychological outcomes, physical health issues, and labor market decisions, and understanding it can offer crucial insight into subtle but highly damaging forms of discrimination (Small and Pager 2020). Nevertheless, this approach leaves open the interesting possibility that individuals might perceive or recall discrimination differently when it happens remotely versus on-site. For instance, people tend to remember high-affect events more readily than low-affect ones (Ochsner 2000). If the same discrimination experiences are charged with stronger emotions when they occur in person, then people may experience them as more memorable. This tendency may make women more likely to recall gender discrimination on-site, even if the same thing happened remotely.

Another possibility is that, in remote work, discriminatory behaviors are less noticeable. For example, imagine a male worker who ignores his female colleagues' ideas in meetings by slouching in his chair and texting rather than listening. In an in-person meeting, this expression of everyday gender discrimination would be easily expressed and readily observed. In a video meeting, his slouching and texting would be less noticeable. And in a telephone conference call, his behavior would be invisible. While he might look for other ways of expressing disdain virtually, such as an online chat comment, physical manifestations of discrimination become less transmissible, potentially reducing the likelihood that women experience everyday gender discrimination remotely.

These possibilities open an interesting line of research questions: Do women experience the same gender discrimination incidents as more visceral when they happen on-site? Do they recall such experiences more readily when they happen on-site? Do they respond differently to discrimination based on their expectations about where it occurs? Are they less able to observe the same discriminatory

behaviors when they occur remotely? The ideal study design for answering such questions would involve experiments in which trained actors discriminate against women in exactly the same way remotely and on-site. As prior studies have demonstrated, using trained actors to isolate the effects of discrimination in person (Pager et al. 2009) and online (Owens 2022) presents a formidable methodological challenge. While such an endeavor falls beyond the scope of the present study, we see this as a promising avenue for future research that would build on insights from our findings.

Conclusion

In recent years, white-collar work has transcended traditional office boundaries. With the rapid emergence of remote and hybrid work models, professionals now work in a diverse array of locations, ranging from traditional offices to homes, cafes, and coworking hubs. In light of this evolution, understanding workers' experiences in various work locations becomes crucial. Our research reveals that location—in concert with individual and contextual characteristics—powerfully shapes the prevalence of everyday gender discrimination, a common and consequential experience in many professional women's lives. Remote work serves as a refuge for many women, reducing their exposure to everyday workplace discrimination.

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Figure 1. Gender Composition of Participants' Interaction Partners in On-site and Remote Work

Notes. $N = 1,091$ individuals (main survey respondents) with 2,182 observations.

Figure 2. Percentage of Professional Women with Hybrid Jobs Reporting Everyday Gender Discrimination Experiences by Location

Notes. $N = 1,091$ individuals (main survey respondents) with 2,182 observations. z-scores are derived from tests of proportions. Across all experiences, the percentage of respondents reporting discrimination on-site is significantly higher than remotely. *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$.

Figure 3. Predicted Probabilities of Experiencing Everyday Gender Discrimination by Age Group in On-site and Remote Locations

Notes. $N = 1,091$ individuals (main survey respondents) with 2,182 observations.

Figure 4. Predicted Probabilities of Experiencing Everyday Gender Discrimination by Gender Composition of Interaction Partners in On-site and Remote Locations

Notes. $N = 1,091$ individuals (main survey respondents) with 2,182 observations.

Figure 5. Reported Frequency of On-site and Remote Monitoring

Notes. $N = 1,091$ individuals (main survey respondents) with 2,182 observations. Responses are to the following question: “When working [on-site/remotely], how often are your and your co-workers’ behaviors and interactions observed, examined, and/or recorded, with or without technological assistance, by your supervisor or someone else in the organization?”

Table 1. Types of Everyday Gender Discrimination

#	Shorthand	Colleagues or clients...	Remote Examples	On-site Examples
1	Personality	make negative assumptions about your personality because of your gender	In a virtual meeting, a colleague comments that a female co-worker is "too emotional" to lead an important sales call.	In an in-person meeting, a colleague comments that a female co-worker is "too emotional" to lead an important sales call.
2	Commitment	make negative assumptions about your commitment to your job because of your gender	In a virtual meeting, a supervisor tells a female employee that she'll be given a less valued task so that she can spend more time with family.	In an in-person meeting, a supervisor tells a female employee that she'll be given a less valued task so that she can spend more time with family.
3	Underestimated	treat you as if you were not competent or underestimate your abilities because of your gender	In a virtual meeting, a female employee shares her recommendations with a client. The client then asks a less-experienced male colleague for his opinion.	In an in-person meeting, a female employee shares her recommendations with a client. The client then asks a less-experienced male colleague for his opinion.
4	Picked On	make fun of or pick on you because of your gender	In a slack channel, a member of a remote team writes that a pregnant female employee is a "baby factory."	During a lunchtime team meeting, a member jokes that a pregnant female employee is a "baby factory."
5	Inappropriate Attention	give you unwanted sexual attention or make inappropriate sexual comments	A client sends a female employee a sexually explicit message over WhatsApp.	A client makes a sexually explicit comment to a female employee during a site visit.
6	Ideas Ignored	ignore your ideas or treat them as if they don't matter because of your gender	While working collaboratively in a google doc, colleagues do not address the concerns written in comments by a female employee.	While in a brainstorming meeting, colleagues do not address the concerns voiced by a female employee.
7	Ideas Stolen	fail to give you credit for your ideas or steal your ideas because of your gender	While working collaboratively in a google doc, a female employee makes a suggestion. A colleague later makes the same suggestion to their supervisor without crediting her.	While in a brainstorming meeting, a female employee makes a suggestion. A colleague later makes the same suggestion to their supervisor without crediting her.
8	Unrelated Tasks	ask you to perform tasks unrelated to your job because of your gender	A supervisor asks a female employee to take notes during a virtual meeting, when doing so is not part of her job.	A supervisor asks a female employee to take notes during an in-person meeting, when doing so is not part of her job.
9	Excluded	exclude you from informal groups or work activities because of your gender	A group of male colleagues from a small team form a WhatsApp group and do not invite the one female colleague from that team.	A group of male colleagues from a small team regularly meet for lunch and do not invite the one female colleague from that team.

10	Jokes Shared	share inappropriate jokes, memes, or other comments about your gender	In a Facebook group designed to coordinate work activities, a colleague posts a meme about women being less intelligent than men.	Next to a whiteboard where team members track sales, a colleague posts a cartoon about women being less intelligent than men.
11	Sexist Name	call you a sexist name	A client calls a female employee "sweetie" during a virtual meeting.	A client calls a female employee "sweetie" during an on-site meeting.

Note. Examples are adapted from those provided by participants in Supplemental Survey A and the main survey in open-text responses about personal experiences with everyday gender discrimination. The survey instrument we used in our main survey to measure everyday gender discrimination is available at <https://doi.org/10.5683/SP3/TMIDWR>.

Table 2. Summary Statistics: Means, Standard Deviations, and Correlations

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1. Everyday Gender Discrimination	0.24	0.43	1.00														
2. Remote Location	0.5	0.5	-0.16	1.00													
3. Age Under 30	0.3	0.46	-0.01	0.00	1.00												
4. Gender of Interaction Partners	1.69	1.07	0.19	-0.05	-0.04	1.00											
5. High Monitoring	0.18	0.39	0.12	0.00	-0.03	0.05	1.00										
6. Manager	0.43	0.5	0.12	0.00	-0.16	0.08	0.09	1.00									
7. Frequent Informal Interactions	0.37	0.48	0.07	-0.30	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.06	1.00								
8. Frequent Formal Interactions	0.72	0.45	0.09	-0.25	-0.03	0.00	0.10	0.06	0.30	1.00							
9. % Time On-Site	52.14	23.8	0.03	0.00	0.05	-0.04	0.03	-0.01	0.04	-0.02	1.00						
10. White	0.74	0.44	0.02	0.00	-0.08	-0.02	-0.06	-0.01	0.00	-0.05	0.00	1.00					
11. Married	0.45	0.5	0.01	0.00	-0.36	0.04	0.03	0.16	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.05	1.00				
12. Motherhood	0.38	0.49	0.07	0.00	-0.36	0.05	0.09	0.21	0.02	0.04	0.01	-0.04	0.40	1.00			
13. University Education	0.8	0.4	0.00	0.00	0.03	-0.08	-0.06	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.05	-0.04	1.00		
14. Organization >1000 Employees	0.32	0.47	-0.04	0.00	0.01	0.04	-0.02	-0.13	0.02	0.00	-0.13	-0.02	-0.05	-0.06	0.13	1.00	
15. Part-time Worker	0.13	0.33	-0.03	0.00	0.12	-0.04	0.01	-0.12	-0.07	-0.08	-0.04	0.01	-0.07	-0.02	-0.16	-0.14	1.00

Notes. $N = 1,091$ individuals with 2,182 observations. 34% of the 1,091 respondents experienced some form of everyday gender discrimination. Because not all respondents experienced discrimination in both locations ($N = 2,182$), the mean value of *Everyday Gender Discrimination* (0.24 or 24%) is lower than 34%.

Table 3. Predicting Everyday Gender Discrimination

Variables	Model 1	Model 2
Remote Location	-0.11*** (0.02)	-0.73*** (0.09)
Gender of Interaction Partners		
<i>Slightly more women than men</i>	0.09 (0.05)	1.21*** (0.25)
<i>Men and women equally</i>	0.05 (0.05)	1.09*** (0.25)
<i>Slightly more men</i>	0.22*** (0.06)	1.79*** (0.26)
<i>Only or mostly men</i>	0.28*** (0.08)	2.20*** (0.29)
Age Under 30		0.10 (0.16)
High Monitoring	0.01 (0.03)	0.59*** (0.13)
Manager		0.47*** (0.14)
Frequent Informal Interactions	0.02 (0.02)	-0.01 (0.12)
Frequent Formal Interactions	0.05* (0.02)	0.28 (0.15)
% Time On-site		0.00 (0.00)
White		0.19 (0.15)
Married		-0.17 (0.14)
Motherhood		0.26 (0.15)
University Education		0.13 (0.17)
Organization >1000 Employees		-0.18 (0.14)
Part-time Worker		-0.11 (0.22)
Constant	0.15*** (0.05)	-2.97*** (0.36)
Fixed Effects	Yes	No

Notes. $N = 2182$ observations for 1091 individuals. The reference group for remote location is on-site; the reference group for the gender of interaction partners is “only or mostly women.” *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$.

Table 4. Predicting the Likelihood of Everyday Gender Discrimination with Interaction Effects

Variables	Model 1	Model 2
Remote Location	-0.00 (0.04)	-0.16 (0.40)
Age Under 30		0.27 (0.17)
Remote Location X Age Under 30	-0.06* (0.03)	-0.43* (0.19)
Gender of Interaction Partners		
<i>Slightly more women than men</i>	0.14** (0.05)	1.35*** (0.32)
<i>Men and women equally</i>	0.11 (0.06)	1.28*** (0.32)
<i>Slightly more men</i>	0.29*** (0.07)	1.98*** (0.34)
<i>Only or mostly men</i>	0.44*** (0.09)	2.77*** (0.39)
Remote Location X Gender of Interaction Partners		
<i>Remote X Slightly more women than men</i>	-0.07 (0.05)	-0.33 (0.44)
<i>Remote X Men and women equally</i>	-0.09* (0.04)	-0.44 (0.43)
<i>Remote X Slightly more men</i>	-0.11* (0.05)	-0.42 (0.45)
<i>Remote X Only or mostly men</i>	-0.30*** (0.07)	-1.29* (0.54)
Constant	0.09 (0.05)	-3.22*** (0.41)
Control Variables ^a	Yes	Yes
Fixed Effects	Yes	No

Notes. $N = 2182$ observations for 1091 individuals. The reference group for remote location is on-site; the reference group for the gender of interaction partners is “only or mostly women.” *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$.

^a Both models control for *high monitoring, infrequent formal interactions, and frequent formal interactions*. In addition, Model 2 controls for location-invariant factors: *manager, % time on-site, white, married, motherhood, university education, organization > 1000 employees, and part-time worker*.

Table A. Initial List of Everyday Gender Discrimination

#	Colleagues or clients...
1	make negative assumptions about your personality based on gender stereotypes
2	treat you as if you were not competent because of your gender
3	ignore your ideas or treat them as if they didn't matter because of your gender
4	exclude you from informal groups or work activities because of your gender
5	share inappropriate jokes or memes about your gender
6	give you unwanted sexual attention or make inappropriate sexual comments
7	call you a sexist name
8	mock, mimic, or pick on you because of your gender
9	threaten you with harm (physical or otherwise) because of your gender

Table B. Robustness Checks with Three Alternative Samples

Variables	Model 1 (Completely Similar Tasks)	Model 2 (Someone Else Determines Work Location)	Model 3 (50% or Less Time Spent On-Site)
Remote Location	-0.08** (0.03)	-0.14*** (0.03)	-0.07*** (0.02)
Gender of Interaction Partners			
<i>Slightly more women than men</i>	0.03 (0.09)	0.17* (0.07)	-0.00 (0.06)
<i>Men and women equally</i>	-0.04 (0.10)	0.13 (0.08)	-0.03 (0.07)
<i>Slightly more men</i>	0.11 (0.11)	0.42*** (0.09)	0.13 (0.08)
<i>Only or mostly men</i>	-0.07 (0.15)	0.26 (0.14)	0.36*** (0.11)
High Monitoring	-0.01 (0.06)	0.04 (0.05)	0.00 (0.04)
Frequent Informal Interactions	0.05 (0.04)	0.01 (0.04)	0.03 (0.03)
Frequent Formal Interactions	0.04 (0.05)	0.05 (0.04)	0.08* (0.03)
Constant	0.19* (0.09)	0.11 (0.07)	0.17* (0.07)
Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>N</i>	638	852	1144

Notes. The reference group for remote location is on-site; the reference group for the gender of interaction partners is “only or mostly women.” Because all models include individual fixed effects, they account for location-invariant characteristics, including *age under 30, motherhood, manager, % time spent on-site, white, married, university education, organization > 1000 employees, and part-time worker.* *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$.

Appendix A. Recruitment Strategy for Hybrid Worker Survey

We adopted two sampling approaches to recruit female, professional workers with hybrid arrangements.

SAMPLING APPROACH 1

We invited participants who met the following criteria on Prolific:

1. Affirmed in a standard Prolific prescreening question that “I sometimes work from a central place of work and sometimes remotely.”
2. Identified as women between ages 18-75 located in the United States.
3. Indicated that they were currently employed in professional roles, including upper management, middle management, junior management, trained professional, consultant, researcher, self-employed/partner, support staff, or administrative staff.

SAMPLING APPROACH 2

Our second approach accounts for the fact that hybrid work arrangements can change quickly. Some women who did not have hybrid arrangements when they completed the standard Prolific prescreening question about hybrid work (item 1 above) might have since transitioned to a hybrid arrangement without updating their profile. To ensure that women with more recent hybrid arrangements were also represented, we ran an additional survey to identify professional women who met sampling criteria (2) and (3) above, but did not affirm that they had a hybrid arrangement in the Prolific prescreening question (item 1). In that short survey, we asked:

Please consider whether you worked **remotely** (for example, from home or a coffee shop), **on-site** (for example, an office or other central site), or **in both locations** in the past month. If you have more than one job, consider only your main job.

Which of the following best describes your **most recent month at work**?

- I worked **entirely REMOTELY** and did not work from an office or central site.
- I worked **entirely ON-SITE** and did not work from a remote location.
- I worked **both REMOTELY and ON-SITE**. I spent some of my time working from a remote location and some of my time at an office or central site.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

We invited those who indicated that they worked both remotely and on-site to participate. Respondents from both sampling approaches took the same survey. Our decision to invite respondents via the second approach was theoretically motivated. We recognized that many workers were undergoing post-pandemic

changes in work arrangements around the time of our May 2023 survey; we wanted to ensure that we did not systematically exclude workers whose hybrid arrangements emerged more recently. As an additional assurance that respondents were currently engaged in hybrid work, we had all survey participants confirm at the outset that they had a hybrid arrangement in the past month.

The majority (82%) of respondents came from the first sampling approach. Comparing respondents recruited via approaches 1 and 2, we find non-significant differences on key characteristics. Respondents from both approaches do not differ significantly in their likelihood of experiencing everyday gender discrimination in the past month ($t = -0.58, p = .56$). We also re-ran Model 1, Table 3 and included an interaction term for *remote work X sampling approach*. We found a non-significant coefficient ($\beta = -0.01, p = .677$), suggesting a non-significant difference between participants from each sampling approach and their difference in likelihood of discrimination between locations. Further, results of two-sided *t*-tests confirm non-significant differences between respondents from each sampling approach on age ($t = 0.05, p = .96$), gender composition of the interaction set ($t = 1.67, p = .10$), and percentage of time spent on-site ($t = 0.92, p = .36$). These results suggest that respondents recruited via the two different approaches do not differ in ways that would meaningfully affect our overall findings.

Appendix B. Exploring Differences in Everyday Gender Discrimination Experiences by Location

In a series of exploratory analyses, we investigated whether different types of women (younger versus older; those whose interaction partner sets reflect different gender compositions) reported different types of everyday gender discrimination by location. We began by considering differences between younger and older women. We found that being underestimated was the most commonly reported type of discrimination for both age groups and in both locations. However, the second most common type of on-site discrimination differs by age group. When working on-site, women under 30 reported personality-related discrimination as the second most common form, whereas women over 30 reported being asked to perform tasks unrelated to their jobs. Thus, when working on-site, younger and older women have somewhat different discrimination experiences. Otherwise, younger and older women experience similar types of everyday gender discrimination in both locations.

Next, we examined the types of everyday gender discrimination experienced by women with primarily male versus primarily female interaction partners.¹¹ We found that the most frequent types of discrimination—being underestimated and personality-related discrimination—are consistent across locations regardless of the predominant gender of women’s interaction partners. However, one type of discrimination differed between groups: being excluded from informal groups or work activities. Women interacting mainly with other women rarely reported being excluded (1% on-site and 1% remotely). However, among women with primarily male interaction partners, 11% reported being excluded on-site and 4% remotely. It appears that women with primarily male interaction partners are more likely to be excluded, particularly when working on-site. This finding echoes research demonstrating that female professionals are often excluded from male-dominated social engagements and informal professional gatherings, which often take place in-person (e.g., Morgan and Martin 2006). But despite this difference,

¹¹ Women with primarily male interaction partners work with *only or mostly men* or *slightly more men than women*. Women with primarily female interaction partners work with *only or mostly women* or *slightly more women than men*.

ONLINE SUPPLEMENT

women's experiences of everyday gender discrimination were quite consistent across gender composition groups and remote versus on-site locations.

Appendix C. Supplemental Survey C: Work Preferences

In September 2023, we invited all Prolific participants who completed our main survey to take a “short survey about work preferences.” We were able to resample 55.9% of the original survey participants, yielding a total of 610 respondents for our supplemental survey. Using a 7-point scale, participants rated the extent to which they preferred remote versus on-site work (7 = strongly prefer working on-site, 4 = equally prefer working remotely and working on-site, 1 = strongly prefer working remotely).

We took several steps to ensure that our measurement of everyday gender discrimination (captured in our main survey) did not bias, and was not biased by, our measurement of participants’ general preferences for remote versus on-site work. First, we fielded the supplemental survey (focused on participants’ general preference for on-site versus remote work) as a separate survey. This was advantageous because asking participants about both issues in the same survey and at the same time might have biased their responses. For example, asking numerous questions about gender discrimination and thus strongly focusing participants’ attention on that issue might have led them to overstate their preference for the location in which they experienced less discrimination. Second, we obscured connections between the two surveys. Invitation to the main survey came from the first author, and invitations to the supplemental survey came from the second author. Third, to further obscure the purpose of the supplemental survey, we included our question of interest next to two filler questions, focused on preferences for routine versus creative tasks and preferences for frequent versus infrequent feedback at work.